

CHO'LPON LIRIKASIDA HAYVONLAR RAMZI

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Annotatsiya: ushbu maqolada Abdulhamid Sulaymon o'g'li Cho'lponning fauna olami aks etgan she'rlari tahlilga tortilgan. Shoirning "Buzilgan o'lkaga", "Ko'klam qayg'usi", "So'lgan choqlarda", "Sozim" kabi she'rlarida hayvonlar obrazining o'ziga xos tarzda ifoda yo'sini yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: jadid, lirika, ilohiy muhabbat, samoviy zavqlar, poda, yilqi, sor burgutlar

Kirish. Abdulhamid Cho'lpon ijodiga nazar solsak, uning naqadar mahoratli ijodkor ekanligi, o'z davri adabiy muhiti uchun muhim bo'lgan manbalarni bera olganligiga beixtiyor amin bo'lamiz. Shoir she'rlarida mavjud barcha obrazlar yuqori darajada tasvirlangan. Ayniqsa, adib she'rlarida tabiat va hayvonlar obrazi keng yoritilgan. Albatta, boshqa yozuvchi va shoirlar ijodida fauna olami tasvirlari ko'p uchraydi. Ammo Cho'lpon ijodida bu kabi obrazlarga yangicha ma'no qirralari yuklanganiga guvoh bo'lamiz.

Cho'lpon chinakam o'zbek shoiri hisoblanadi. Uni nafaqat ijodkor, balki jadid sifatida ham faoliyat yuritganini yaxshi bilamiz. U butun millat ravnaqi uchun o'z jonini fido qilgan vatanparvar hisoblanadi. O'z davrida Cho'lpon ijodi, uning asarlari ta'qib ostiga olingan. Uni "millatchi", "xalq dushmani" sifatida qoralab, asarlarini yo'qotishga uringanlar. Ammo zamonlar o'tishi bilan Cho'lpon asarlarining asl g'oyasi ochiqlandi. Ya'ni uning xalq uchun borini fido etganligi isbotlandi. Shoir yozgan asarlari xalqni ma'naviy jihatdan yuksaltirdi. Ming tassufki, aynan shu fidoyiligi, xalqparvarligi uchun ham "xalq dushmani" sifatida ayblanib qatag'on qilingan edi.

Cho'lpon ijodining barchasi juda yuksak mahorat bilan yozilgan. Uning she'rlarida haqiqat, erkka tashnalik, vatanga bo'lgan cheksiz muhabbat ufurib turadi.

Shoir she'rlarini o'qigan har bir kishining qalbida ajib hislar paydo bo'ladi. Ular kitobxonni beixtiyor o'ziga maftun etadi.

Cho'lpon she'rlarida, ayniqsa, hayvonlar obrazi ramziy ma'no ifodalash jihatidan ustunlik kasb etadi. Bu ham shoir ijodining individual xususiyatlarga egaligini ko'rsatadi. Quyidagi misralarni namuna tariqasida keltirish mumkin:

Ko'm-ko'k, go'zal o'tloqlaring bosilg'on,
Ustlarida na poda bor, na yilqi,
Podachilar qaysi dorg'a osilg'on?
Ot kishnashi, qo'y ma'rashi o'rniga
– Oh, yig'i
Bu nega?

Dastlabki ikki misrada peyjaz tasviri berilgan. Aslida, bahorda butun olam yasharadi, atrofda, borliqda go'zallik alomatlari namoyon bo'ladi. Barcha dala va qirlarda ishlar avj oladi. Podachilar va yilqilar dalalarda kezib yuradi. Lekin keyingi misralarda shu ayon bo'ladiki, bu safargi bahorda bunday tarovat yo'q. Ya'ni yurtda qandaydir talofat yoki urush bo'lgan. Shu sababli dalalarda hech kim yo'q. Otlar kishnamay, qo'ylar ma'ramay qo'ygan:

Ot minganda, qushlar kabi uchguvchi,
Erkin-erkin havolarni qurguvchi,
Ot chopganda, uchar qushni tutquvchi,
Uchar qushday yosh yigitlar qayerda?
Tog' egasi – sor burgutlar qayerda?

Ushbu she'riy parchada faunistik obrazlar ramziy ma'no tashigan. Bunda insonlarga xos xatti-harakat, xususiyat va sifatlar hayvonlarga ko'chirilgan. Yurt egasi – mard o'glonlar tog' egasi – sor burgutlarga qiyoslangan. Bu qiyos orqali tashbeh san'ati hosil qilingan. Shoir xalq dardini kuyunib she'rga slogan, ya'ni yurt boshiga og'ir tashvishlar tushganda uni himoya qilguvchi mardlar qayerda, deya hayqirmoqda shoir. Cho'lpon ijodiga xos o'zgachalik shundan ma'lum bo'ladiki, ijodkor bir fikr bilan ikki masalani ko'tarib chiqqan. Bu nima degani? Yurti tinch bo'lmagan o'lkada, hattoki qushlar ham erkin ucholmaydi. Bundan tashqari “sor burgutlar” degan birikmaga ham alohida e'tibor qaratishimiz lozim. Ma'lumki, burgut eng kuchli va baquvvat qush hisoblanadi. Yosh yigitlar ham jasur, mard va baquvvat bo'ladi. Tog' egasi hisoblanmish sor burgutlarning o'z vatanini himoya qilgani kabi nega bizning yigitlarimiz yurt himoyasida sodiq emas? O'lka tinchligi, millat erki uchun kurash ketayotgan bir davrda nega ular ko'rinmaydi, nega bir yoqadan bosh chiqarmaydi kabi turli savollar shoirni qiynaydi. Bu o'rinda Cho'lpon burgut obrazini majoziy ma'noda qo'llab, unga ramziylik yukini ortgan. Va albatta,

bu mavzu, bu g'oya shoir she'rlarining deyarli barchasida qizil chiziq kabi ko'rinish berib turadi.

Cho'lponning "Ko'klam qayg'usi" she'ridan olingan ushbu misralar ham ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan mazkr mulohazalarimizni tasdiqlaydi:

Ko'klam chog'i... Sayroq bulbul sayramas,
Na uchunkim, tanburimning tili yo'q.
Ul go'zal qiz chin qarash-la qaramas,
Na uchunkim, umidimning yo'li yo'q.

Bu o'rinda nafaqat bulbul obrazi, balki bir go'zal yor – inson obrazi ham she'rning badiiy go'zal chiqishini ta'minlagan. Albatta, bu yerda ham bahor tasviri keng yoritilgan. Shoirning o'ziga xos uslubidan darak beruvchi yana bir jihat shundaki, u insonning his-kechinmalari, dardi, alami, qayg'usini tabiat fasllariga bog'lab aks ettirishda mohirdir.

Ko'klamni bezovchi eng muhim vosita bulbul obrazi sanaladi. Usiz bahor bahormas, aslida. Ko'klam chog'i birikmasi so'ngida uch nuqtaning qo'yilishi ham bejizga emas. Bulbul bor-u sayramaydi. Nega, degan savol tug'iladi. Chunki uning ovozi bo'g'ilgan. Misralar qatiga singdirilgan ma'nodan uqish mumkinki, bu o'rinda bulbul shoir obrazini gavdalandirgan. Ushbu ramziy qiyos Cho'lpon g'oyalarining badiiy in'ikos etishida qo'l kelgan.

Ta'kidlash joizki, shoirning "Sozim" she'ri ham g'oyaviy jihatdan yuqoridagi lirika namunalariga yaqin turadi. Ushbu she'rda tabiat hamda hayvonlar timsoli yordamida sevgi mavzusi yoritilgan. Cho'lpon juda kuchli ijodkor bo'lganligi sababli, o'z lirikasida ham tabiat, ham vatan, ham ilohiy muhabbat tuyg'ularini birdek jamlay oladi:

Samoviy zavqlarga to'lib turganman
Bulbullar sevgini maqtagan damda!

E'tibor beradigan bo'lsak, bu she'rda bulbul va sevgi tushunchalari yonma-yon qo'llangan. Bunda shoir an'anaviy tamoyillarga amal qilgan. Folklor namunalarida ham, mumtoz asarlarda ham ushbu misralardagi kabi bulbul obrazi oshiq, yor obrazlari bilan bir o'rinda ishlatilib, badiiy mukammallik ta'minlangan.

Xulosa. Qayd etish joizki, Abdulhamid Sulaymon o'g'li Cho'lpon garchi uzoq yashamagan bo'lsa-da, o'zidan boy adabiy meros qoldirishga ulgurdi. Uning lirikasi, qolaversa boshqa adabiy turga mansub asarlari kishilar ongini uyg'otishga xizmat qiladi, xalqni ma'rifatga chorlaydi. Zamonaviy o'zbek adabiyotida ramziy ifodalarga eng ko'p murojaat etgan ijodkorlar qatorida Cho'lponning ham e'tirof etilishi tabiiydir. Chunki uning ijodi qanday mavzu bo'lishidan qat'i nazar majoziy,

ramziy-timsoliy obrazlarga boy. Kitobxonga asosiy g'oyani yetkazishda bu kabi go'zal tasvirlardan foydalanish shoir she'rlarining leytmotivini tashkil etadi.

ADABIYOTLAR:

1. Akhmedova, Shoira, and Sofiya Mahmudova. "ABU ALI IBN SINA ON A CRITICAL BIOGRAPHICAL ESSAY." *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences* 2.7 (2022): 795-799
2. NEMATOVNA, AKHMEDOVA SHOIRA, KADYROVA NASIMA SAIDBURKHONOVNA, and KURBANOVA OLTINOY BEKMURODOVNA. "METHODOLOGY AND SKILLS PROBLEMS." *The journal of contemporary issues in business and government* 27.5 (2021): 778-784.
3. Nematovna, Akhmedova Shoira. "GENRE OF LITERARY PORTRAIT IN THE WORKS OF ALISHER NAVAI." *SCIENTIFIC REPORTS OF BUKHARA STATE UNIVERSITY НАУЧНЫЙ ВЕСТНИК БУХАРСКОГО ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА*: 127
4. Axmedova, Shoira. "THE ROLE OF THE JADID PRESS IN THE FORMATION OF UZBEK LITERARY CRITICISM." *Конференции*. 2021.
5. Ахмедова, Ш. Н., & Назарова, Д. (2021). АДАБИЙ ПОРТРЕТ ЖАНРИНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ЖИХАТЛАРИ ХУСУСИДА. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 4(3).
6. Ахмедова, Шоира Нематовна. "ЎЗБЕК ВА ФРАНЦУЗ АДАБИЁТШУНОСЛИГИДА ПОРТРЕТНАВИСЛИК ТАРАҚҚИЁТИ." *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА* 3.6 (2020).
7. Ахмедова, Шоира. "БУХОРО ТАРИХИГА БАҒИШЛАНГАН ШЕЪРЛАР ҲАҚИДА." *FILOLOGIYA UFQLARI JURNALI* 6.6 (2021).
8. Ахмедова Ш. Н. ХУРШИД ДАВРОННИНГ АДАБИЙ–ЭСТЕТИК ҚАРАШЛАРИ: Ахмедова Шоира Нематовна, БухДУ ўзбек адабиёти кафедраси профессори, ф. ф. доктори //Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал. – 2022. – №. 6.2. Махсус сон. – С. 20-28.
9. Ахмедова, Шоира Нематова. "ПРОГРЕСС ПОРТРЕТОПИСАНИЯ В ПЕРИОД ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ В ЛИТЕРАТУРОВЕДЕНИИ." *Россия-Узбекистан. Международные образовательные и социально-культурные технологии: векторы развития* (2019): 12-14.

10. Ахмедова, Шоира Нематовна, Лосеева-Танем Бахтияри, and Насима Саидбурхановна Кадирова. "О Творческой Специфике Литературной Критики." *Miasto Przyszłości* 42 (2023): 326-329.
11. Shokhsanam Davronova 2021. UZBEK NOVEL IN THE INDEPENDENCE PERIOD: TRADITION AND NOVELTY ISSUES. *JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*. (Feb. 2021), 679–683.
12. Davronova S. Eastern and western literary tradition in the modern uzbek novels //World science. – 2016. – Т. 4. – №. 5 (9). – С. 33-34.
13. Davronova S. MODERN ÖZBEK ROMANLARINDA KÂMİL İNSAN TERBİYESİ MESELESİNİN ELE ALINIŞI //Electronic Turkish Studies. – 2017. – Т. 12. – №. 15.
14. DAVRONOVA S. TARİHİ ROMANDA MUTASAVVIF BİLGİN SİMASI //DİL VE EDEBİYAT ARAŞTIRMALARI I. – С. 108.
15. Shohsanam D. EASTERN AND WESTERN LITERARY TRADITION IN THE MODERN UZBEK NOVELS //International Scientific and Practical Conference World science. – ROST, 2016. – Т. 4. – №. 5. – С. 33-34.
16. Давронова Ш. Литературное влияние и творчество //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2016. – Т. 1. – №. 2 (59). – С. 40-46.
17. Давронова Ш. Адабий таъсир ва ижодийлик //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование.–2016. – 2016.
18. Davronova S. КОНТРАСТИЧЕСКОЕ ОПИСАНИЕ МЕТОДА В ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ РАССКАЗА ИСАДЖАНА СУЛТАНА “ОЛИСДАГИ УРУШНИНГ АКС-САДОСИ”(«ЭХО ВОЙНЫ ВДАЛЕКЕ»)) //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2022. – Т. 9. – №. 9.
19. Davronova S. Mythology in intellectual novels //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2015. – №. 4. – С. 40-43.
20. Gaybulloevna D. S., Bakhtiyorovna N. N. PSYCHOLOGIST IN ULUGBEK HAMDAM'S NOVEL" FATHER.
21. Davronova S., Kandimova I. CHARACTER CREATION SKILLS OF LUKMON BORIKHAN //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 30-34.
22. O'roqova, N. (2024). ABDULLA ORIPOV LIRIKASIDA RAMZIY-FLORISTIK OBRAZLAR IFODASI. Центральноеазиатский журнал междисциплинарных исследований и исследований в области управления, 1(3), 193-199.

23. O'roqova, N. (2024). SADRIDDIN AYNIY USLUBIGA DOIR CHIZGILAR. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 47(47).
извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/12188
24. O'roqova N. О 'ZBEK SHE'RIYATIDA KAPALAK OBRAZI TALQINI //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2024. – Т. 47. – №. 47.
25. Yorievna, U. N. ., & Ikhtiyar's , K. N. . (2024). National Portrait in Otkir Hashimov's Stories. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 3(3), 831–837. Retrieved from <https://www.bjisrd.com/index.php/bjisrd/article/view/1923>
26. Nafosat, U., & Quvvatova, D. (2019). An untraditional description style in the epos of Ikrom Otamurod. International Journal of Engineering and Advanced Technology, 8(5 Special Issue 3), 396-399.
27. Uroкова, N. (2019). GENRE RESEARCH IN UZBEK POEMS OF RECENT TIMES. Theoretical & Applied Science, (8), 57-59.
28. Uroкова, N. (2022). MASNAVI IN MODERN UZBEK PROSE. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 1(3), 63-65.
29. Yorievna, U. N. (2022). Masnavi Genre in Uzbek Classical Poetry: Nature, Genesis, Features. Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture, 3(10), 67-70.
30. Yoriyevna, U. N. (2023). THE ORIGINALITY AND GENESIS OF ANIMAL SYMBOLISM IN POETRY. Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development, 18, 20-23.
31. Уракова, Н. (2019). Стиль писателя в современных узбекских поэмах. International scientific review, (1 (41)), 26-28.
32. Uroкова, N. (2019). GENRE RESEARCH IN UZBEK POEMS OF RECENT TIMES. Theoretical & Applied Science, (8), 57-59.
33. O'roqova, N. (2019). So'nggi yillar o'zbek dostonchiligida ijodkor uslubi va individualligi (I. Otamurod va U. Qo'chqor dostonlari asosida). Falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) dissertatsiyasi, Qarshi, 2019. B, 21
34. Yoriyevna, U. N. (2023). RELATIONSHIPS BETWEEN HUMANS AND ANIMALS. Confrencea, 8(1), 123-126.
35. O'roqova , N. . (2022). О'ZBEK MUMTOZ SHE'RIYATIDA MASNAVIY JANRI TABIATI, GENEZISI, XUSUSIYATLARI. Евразийский журнал социальных наук, философии и культуры, 2(10), 38–42. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejsspc/article/view/4041>

36. Yorievna, U. N. ., & Narzulloyevna, M. L. . (2024). Interpretation of the Image of Animals in Abdulla Oripov's Poetry. International Journal of Formal Education, 3(4), 40–45. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/ijfe/article/view/2478>
37. Sayliyeva Z. EY SABO, SHARH AYLA AVVAL DILSITONIMDIN XABAR //Центральноазиатский журнал междисциплинарных исследований и исследований в области управления. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 200-205.
38. Sayliyeva Z. R., Murodova M. R. Q. LITERACY OF PRAISE IN THE VERSES OF ALISHER NAVOI //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 5. – С. 372-380.
39. Rakhmiddinova S. Z., Mahliyo B. FALAK NILUFARLARIDIN CHASHMAYI MEHR GAR O'LDI PAYDO //E Conference Zone. – 2022. – С. 93-96.
40. Rakhmiddinova S. Z. The Study of the Problems of Sufizm and Art in Navoi Studies //Central Asian Journal of Literature, Philosophy and Culture. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 5. – С. 258-262.
41. Rahmiddinova S. Z. et al. OMINA SHENLIKO 'G 'LINING" VIJDON AZOBI" ASARIGA TAQRIZ //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2023. – Т. 33. – №. 2. – С. 90-93.
42. Rakhmiddinova S. Z. EY, SAFHAYI RUXSORING AZAL XATIDIN INSHO //SCIENTIFIC REPORTS OF BUKHARA STATE UNIVERSITY. – С. 112.
43. Raxmiddinova S. Z., Bahromjonovna H. Z. USMON AZIM–ROST TUYG'ULAR KUYCHISI //TADQIQOTLAR. UZ. – 2023. – Т. 26. – №. 1. – С. 3-6.
44. Rakhmiddinova S. Z., Qizi M. M. R. Prophet of the peace and blessings of allah be upon him (o prophet of the prophet hood...) //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 12. – №. 5. – С. 31-36.
45. Rakhmiddinova S. Z., Manzura K. MUHAMMAD RAHIMKHAN FERUZ AND HIS DESCENDANTS //Proceedings of International Conference on Modern Science and Scientific Studies. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 2. – С. 142-146.
46. Rakhmiddinova S. Z. About the Artistic Skills of Alisher Navoi //Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 838-846.

47. Dilbar K., Rakhmiddinova S. Z. "PROMOTER OF MUSLIM CLASSICAL LITERATURE" FORTY HADITH" //International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9.
48. Sodikova T. D. Depiction of Romantic Love in Muslihabegim Miskin's Poetry //Middle European Scientific Bulletin. – 2021. – Т. 8.
49. Содикова Д. Т. ПРОБЛЕСКИ ЖЕНСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ ВО ВРЕМЕНА ДИНАСТИИ БУХАРСКОГО ЭМИРАТА: ВСЕ О ПОЭТЕССЕ МУСЛИХАБЕГИМ МИСКИН И ЕЕ ЛИТЕРАТУРНОМ НАСЛЕДИИ //ББК 81.632 А43. – С. 174.
50. Eshankulov H., Sadikova D. Muslihabegim Miskin is a talented bilingual poetes during the literary period of the XIXth century in Bukhara //GOLDEN SCRIPTS OLTIN BITIGLAR. – С. 41.
51. Садикова Д. MUSLIHABEGIM MISKIN-ALISHER NAVOI'S FOLLOWER //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 8.
52. Sodikova D. MUSLIHABEGIM MISKIN IS A ZULLISONAYN (WHO WROTE HER WORKS IN TWO LANGUAGES) POETESS //Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 81-86.
53. Садикова Д. Muslihabegim Miskin–XIX asr Buxoro adabiy muhitining iste'dodli zullisonayn shoirasi //Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 8.
54. Садикова D. The Expression of Muslikha begim Miskin's Autobiography in Her Own Literary Collections //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2023. – Т. 38. – №. 38.
55. Sodikova D. MUSLIHABEGIM MISKIN IS A ZULLISONAYN (WHO WROTE HER WORKS IN TWO LANGUAGES) POETESS //Журнал академических исследований нового Узбекистана. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 81-86.
56. Садикова D. The Expression of Muslikha begim Miskin's Autobiography in Her Own Literary Collections //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2023. – Т. 38. – №. 38.
57. Eshankulov H., Sadikova D. Muslihabegim Miskin is a talented bilingual poetes during the literary period of the XIXth century in Bukhara //GOLDEN SCRIPTS OLTIN BITIGLAR. – С. 41.
58. Turaeva, L. O. (2021). Artistic and compositional features of harvest songs. *ASIAN JOURNAL OF MULTIDIMENSIONAL RESEARCH*, 10(4), 629-634.

59. To'rayeva, L. O. (2024). O'ZBEK DEHQONCHILIGIDA TAQVIM RAMZLARI. *IMRAS*, 7(1), 779-783.
60. To'rayeva, L. O. (2023). O'ZBEK XALQ OG'ZAKI IJODIDA DEHQON OLQISHLARINING O'ZIGA XOS IFODASI. *O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI*, 2(24), 22-25.
61. To'rayeva, L. O. (2023). DEHQONCHILIK QO'SHIQLARI JANRINI BELGILASHDA KASBIY ATAMALARNING O'RNI. *MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH*, 2(22), 66-70.
62. To'rayeva, L. O. (2022, June). Maqollarda dehqonlar hayotining badiiy talqini. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 71-73).
63. To'rayeva, L. (2021). O'ZBEK ZIROATSHILIGIDA MOSHGA MUNOSABATNING FOLKLORDAGI BADIY TALQINLARI XUSUSIDA. *SYeNTR NAUCHNYYX PUBLIKASIY (buxdu. uz)*, 7(7).
64. Omonovna T. L. Artistic understanding of peasant life in proverbs //Eurasian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences. – 2022. – T. 9. – S. 47-49.
65. TORAYEVA, L. (2023). O'RIM QO'SHIQLARINING OBRAZLAR TARKIBI VA BADIY-KOMPOZISION XUSUSIYATLARI. *SYeNTR NAUCHNYYX PUBLIKASIY (buxdu. uz)*, 42(42).
66. Omonovna, T. L. (2024). A Hymn of Divine Ideas in the Wisdoms of Yassavi. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 3(4), 34-39
67. Raxmatovna T. U., Zaripovna R. R. Study of Begali Kasimov's Activity in Literary Studies and Scientific Biography of the Scientist //Journal of Survey in Fisheries Sciences. – 2023. – T. 10. – №. 2S. – C. 3454-3459.
68. Toraeva U. R. Definition and research methods of Uzbek modern literature //Current research journal of philological sciences. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 10. – C. 104-107.
69. Turaeva U. R. Determination of characteristics of uzbek jadid schools and literature //наука и инновации в ххi веке: актуальные вопросы, открытия и достижения. – 2021. – С. 154-156.
70. Rakhmatovna T. U. UDC: 82.09. 575.1 Literary critic begali kasimov is a researcher of modern literature //scientific reports of bukhara state university. – C. 114.
71. Rakhmatovna T. U. Research of heritage of representatives of uzbek literature of the period of national renaissance //principal issues of scientific research and modern education. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 7.

72. Torayeva U. The Tatar press and Turkestan Jadidism In The researches of Begali Kasimov //Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 8. – №.
73. Torayeva U. O‘zbek jadid adabiyoti va jahon ijtimoiy-adabiy harakatchiligi masalasining tadqiq etilishi //Центральноазиатский журнал междисциплинарных исследований и исследований в области управления. – 2024. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 206-211.
74. Рахматовна Т. У. Study of Begali Kasimov's Activity in Literary Studies and Scientific Biography of the Scientist //Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 869-875.
75. Latipov H. R. ALISHER NAVOI ON LOVE, ENLIGHTENMENT AND AWARENESS //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №. 6. – С. 551-556.
76. Ramazonovich L. H. Souls striving to god or from the world of wise people //Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities Research. – 2018. – Т. 6. – №. 04. – С. 14-18.
77. Baxtiyorovna, N. N. ., & Latipov, H. R. . (2024). Expression of Common Ideas and Images in the Creations of Navoy and Pushkin. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 3(4), 46–53. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/ijfe/article/view/2479>
78. Ramazonovich, L. H. . (2024). Symbolism, Allusion and Essence in the Work of Turkigoi Songs. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 3(4), 20–28. Retrieved from <http://journals.academiczone.net/index.php/ijfe/article/view/2474>